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OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES TO USE ICT IN NEPALESE MATHEMATICS CLASSROOM

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Abstract: *Information and Communication Technology (ICT) plays vigorous role to make mathematics teaching learning activities more meaningful. This paper will try to address the queries: such as what are the opportunities to use ICT in mathematics classroom? What are the challenges or most distressing factors to use ICT in Nepalese mathematics classroom? The paper is divided in to two sections. First section describes about opportunities; effectiveness, efficiency, motivation, simplify abstract knowledge, instructional resources, improve students' performance and achievement and quality, pace and accreditation of learning. Second section describes about challenges; geographical diversity, infrastructures, awareness and attitude, economic, readiness and trained facilitator.*

Keywords: *ICT, Mathematics Education, Opportunities, Challenges.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Information and communication technologies in education refer to teaching and learning of subject matter that enables understanding the functions and effective use of information and communication technologies (ICTs). ICT is a dynamism that has changed many aspects of the way we live. The impact of ICT across the past decades has been enormous. When we look at education, there seems to have been lack of influence and far less change than other fields have experienced. A number of people have attempted to explore this lack of activity and influence even we have more opportunities. There have been a number of factors impeding the wholesale uptake of ICT in education across all sectors. These have included such factors as a lack of training among established teaching practitioners. Lack of motivation and need among teachers to adopt ICT as teaching tools. But, in recent times, factors have emerged which have strengthened and encouraged moves to adopt ICTs into classrooms and learning settings. These factors and many others are bringing strong forces to bear on the adoption of ICTs in education and contemporary trends suggest we will soon see large-scale changes in the way education is planned and delivered as a consequence of the opportunities of ICT.

Nepalese education system yet not seeks to build a pupil centered, development orientated information society. Currently, Ministry of Education Nepal seeks to better incorporate ICT into our schools/colleges/universities etc. including non- formal education.

NCF for School Education in Nepal-2007 states that the human civilization has already entered into the era of ICT and it is a means of receiving and retrieving, storing and collecting, developing and applying, communicating and disseminating knowledge and information as well as ICT has been proved as one of the important tools for promoting education.

We (*Dahal & Dahal*) are professionally interested in the usefulness of ICT as a subject for Mathematics teaching learning and *may* recommend its *inclusion* in the Nepalese curriculum to the Ministry of Education to return. Because we are interested in studying how ICT is used in teaching and learning in Mathematics or any subjects, we will be looking for insights that

may be applied across the curriculum. In this introductory part, we remark on the opportunities and challenges to use ICT in Mathematics classrooms in the context of Nepal.

Here, Opportunities means getting a chance to learn and teach using ICT. Learning depends on the learners' opportunity that means if the learners do not get the opportunities to construct new knowledge then they cannot achieve the goals of learning. Therefore, in teaching learning activities, using ICT is an opportunity for learners as well as facilitators to develop, construct, innovate and explore the new ideas and knowledge of Mathematics. We cannot focus only on opportunities because we have numerous challenges to use ICT. In this paper, the challenge means such types of factors that discourage to use ICT in education especially in mathematics classroom. We are trying to analyze the discouraging factors that hinder the use of ICT in mathematics classroom in the context of Nepal.

We as students as well as teacher of mathematics need to think how we can create environment to learn the absolute and abstract form of mathematics in visualizing and realizing way. To eliminate that problem, we can expect the use of ICT in mathematics classroom (i.e. mathematics teaching learning activities).

2. OPPORTUNITIES IN MATHEMATICS

The continued and increased use of ICTs in education and in mathematics classroom in years to come, will serve to increase the temporal and geographical opportunities that are currently experienced. Advancements in learning opportunities tend to be held back by the ICT capabilities of the lowest common denominator, namely the students with the least access to ICT. As ICT access increases among students. The use of ICT in the mathematics classroom has long been a topic for consideration by mathematics educators. Some examples of ICT use in mathematics include: portables, graphic calculators and computerized graphing, specialized software (Google sketch-up, GeoGebra, Microsoft Mathematics etc.), spreadsheets and databases. It is important and it show that a range of portable devices exists which allow students to collect data, and manipulate by using them. Some portable equipment also enables the study of maths to move out of the classroom and to incorporate fieldwork investigations (Moseley & Higgins, 2011).

Developmental educators have a momentous opportunity to reinvent themselves as resources for the entire in collaborating with the new supplemented learning environment in mathematics classroom. The learning process must be expanded beyond the traditional classroom walls. Additional partners must be added to the learning environment. The ICT program serves as a catalyst for an improved and effective learning environment in mathematics classroom. ICT is flexible tools to meet the learning needs of students and compliment an enriched learning environment managed by the classroom teacher. Through its use, the efficiency and effectiveness of learning can be improved

Students arrive in our classrooms with the full range of motivations and sometimes with what we see as a remarkable lack of motivation. Motivating students is one of the most challenging things we do as educators, and some of us want to throw up our hands in frustration or proclaim, there is little we can do to motivate students to learn. It is true that students carry with them many past experiences that contribute to their motivation in our classrooms. However, teachers can make a difference, for better or for worse, in motivating students to learning. ICT tools in mathematics classroom encourage students to develop problem-solving skills, leads them to develop higher levels of mathematical thinking as well as learn

geometric concepts (Clements, 2013) along with other mathematics concept through demonstration. According to Ittigson and Zewe (2013) ICT supports constructivist pedagogy, which allows students explore and reach an understanding of mathematical concepts. This approach promotes higher order thinking and better problem solving strategies (Ittigson & Zewe, 2013). Voogt (2012) reiterated that teachers can maximize the impact of ICT in mathematics teaching by using ICT as a tool in working towards learning objectives. For mathematics educators, defining the most effective uses of ICT in the teaching of mathematics can certainly be described as a “wicked problem” as represented by Mishra and Koehler (2010).

Thus, in our views ICT is a basic understanding tool to motivate students and to provide some sense of how we can create this motivation. Our ideal goal as teachers is to help students develop the intrinsic motivation that will allow them to become lifelong learners, respect students as learners and engaging students in the class and working with their peers is an important contributor to student learning. There are much such types of abstract, which we can, unable to demonstrate. So, ICT gives such opportunities to simplify the abstract ideas and promote a good environment. An example from Geometry, ‘*when two parallel lines are cut by a transversal, the pairs of alternate interior angles are equal*’. Now the statement is in abstract form but if the learners gate opportunities to learn by using ICT then they can realize and visualize that otherwise it may be only in abstract and drill memorization learning. This is a crucial example of abstract knowledge to visualizing and realizing by using ICT (GeoGebra). In our context, the textbooks as the main sources of knowledge but ICT tool alter. ICT help to increase teaching and learning resources as means in mathematics classroom. In past decades, mathematics teaching is just transmission of knowledge from head to heat and there is not any question. What sort of quality is promoting over but ICT is a tool, which alerts the quality of teaching in the scenario of world context (Moseley & Higgins, 2011).The opportunities of individual and peace learning environment will provide my ICT in mathematics classroom and the level of understanding of each students will reflect.

Accreditation of Learning is generic term used for the award of credits based on demonstrated learning that has taken place in the past. There are two main categories within the accreditation of prior learning. One is ‘the Accreditation of Certificated Learning’ which has been formally assessed and certified by an educational institution or education/training provider and another is ‘the Accreditation of Experiential Learning’ the formal recognition of prior learning gained through other experience, including work, self-directed study or through

leisure pursuits in mathematics learning. At last, ICT helps improve students’ performance, creativity and achievement in mathematics. Through ICT, students will be more active in learning and their desire of learning will fulfill.

3. CHALLENGES FOR ICT

We have numerous rural areas in the nation. Out of the urban sector, up to now we have facing different challenges to use ICT in classroom activities like geographical, educational, cultural as well as economical etc. We mean not that the problems and challenges only in rural sector but urban area have also various factors that create the problem to use ICT in classroom activities. Saritas and Akdemir (2009) states that the quality of teaching and learning mathematics has been one of the major challenges and concerns of educators. Now, what is quality of teaching? Is quality of teaching and effective teaching are similar? May be

these two are similar somewhere so how to teach effectively? May be that is the thinkable question for every teachers of mathematics. By our experiences, if you want to teach effectively the mathematics then there should be use ICT because now a day becomes mathematics and ICT are interrelated to each other.

Definitely, *such* problems are also in our country. For removing such type of problem we need to teach and learn Mathematics through ICT and we already discussed the roles and opportunities of ICT in mathematics classroom. In our context, we are facing various problems and challenges for using ICT in mathematics classroom or in other subjects. Geographically we have Terai region, Hill region and Mountain region. In Mountain region very difficult to manage the basic requirement like as electricity, transportation, network due to weather etc. for using ICT than Terai and Hill region. Terai region somewhere the learners and facilitators get opportunities to use ICT in classroom activities but not so in Hill and Mountain. Therefore, we are facing as challenge to use ICT in the school and university level likewise in Mountain, Hill and Terai region.

Little things play a vital role in somewhere, same as in teaching learning activities there must have different infrastructures for using ICT like as electricity, suitable building, furniture, e-library/ internet, projector, IP board, computer/ laptop etc. Mountain region and many place of Hill region there has no electronic, internet and suitable building facilities up to now then how can we manage the required infrastructure for using technologies in mathematics teaching learning activities? All of us need to think about it also. The readiness and activeness are the main factors for effective teaching learning activities with ICT in mathematics classroom. In this issue, Fitzallen (n.d.) states that the challenge for teachers is to use ICT in ways that promote mathematical thinking and concept development. We think many facilitators in Nepalese education system; they might not know the role of ICT in Mathematics pedagogy. Because of the laziness, may be some facilitators are using the conventional approach in mathematics classroom even though they have sufficient technological instruments. Therefore, we need to develop the positive attitudes or eliminate the laziness for using ICT in mathematics. So we analyzed here the motivation for teaching and learning mathematics with ICT is the current challenge for us.

Nepal is one of the developing country and having constraints to invest in ICT. If the related sectors cannot ready to invest all required efforts to ICT then how can we expect to get respectable output? For using ICT in mathematics teaching learning activities we need to

invest required money at first because there required different software for mathematics and furthermore it need to be update in frequently. In most of the developing country has economic challenge to use ICT in classroom activities as same as in Nepal. Therefore, the gigantic challenge for ICT is economic disasters. Awareness and positive attitude towards technology is widely recognized as a necessary in mathematics for interactive teaching-learning activities. All Nepalese pupils and facilitators may not have such types of awareness and if some conscious about it but they do not try to develop as an attitude for using ICT in mathematics classroom. These are the hidden challenge that we are facing now a day.

The main challenge is lack of ICT proficient course facilitator. We know that our National curriculum formwork-2007 and ICT in education master plan (2013-017) focuses on ICT familiar curriculum in every subject but we need to know our ground reality that is the lack of trained course facilitators for all subjects to use ICT in classroom activities. Especially in mathematics classroom there need to use different mathematical software in different ways so

at first need to provide opportunities for facilitator to gain implementing knowledge and skills of ICT in mathematics.

We analyzed some major challenges for using ICT in Nepalese mathematics classroom. It could not said that there is no provision of ICT in the education system of Nepal but to systematize ICT as a separate subject and as a tool of teaching learning are main problems up to now. It is not our interest but obligation!

4. CONCLUSION

ICTs provide great opportunity for schools/universities in developing countries (Like our) to improve their teaching and learning processes. So far, most of the schools/universities in developing countries possess basic ICT infrastructure such as internet, computers, video, audio, and mobile technology facilities that form the basis for the establishment of E-learning. It argued that, schools/universities in developing countries should adopt e-learning technologies to improve teaching and learning processes. Pedagogical, technical and cost issues should be taken into account for each specific technology when integrating ICTs in teaching and learning practices as challenges.

Therefore, before implementing the ICT familiar curriculum in school to university level, the Ministry of Education Nepal, Curriculum Development Centre and other related sectors need to think for removing the challenges that we are facing. We think at first the Ministry of Education need to make and implement the suitable policies, aware programs, training programs etc. related to ICT and also local educational sectors are also require to actively involve for develop and implement the ICT familiar curriculum in each educational level

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